

Measuring transdisciplinary scope of research project agendas: A network-based approach using the sustainable development goals

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Introduction

The high levels of specialization in science have contributed to the development of multiple areas of knowledge. However, they have also created barriers that sometimes make it difficult to adequately address complex problems. To analyse this kind of problems and the context where they occur researchers work in a different way, promoting communication between the different disciplines and knowledge domains, working in an integrated and collaborative manner, and combining different analytical perspectives for the explanation or solution of these problems (Boon & Van Baalen, 2019). Measuring this disciplinary convergence has become a challenge for scientometricians (Rousseau, Zhang & Hu, 2019). Despite the advances in the development of indicators and methods to identify the multi and interdisciplinary nature of scientific research, there are still numerous limitations (Wang & Schneider, 2020), and the transdisciplinary behaviours are still problems little explored.

This paper aims to measure the multidimensionality of an institutional research project portfolio, based on the analysis of the environment where these projects impact. Bibliometric data and a network-based approach considering the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations (<https://sdgs.un.org/goals>) are used. The SDGs constitute a master plan to achieve a sustainable future, which defines 17 global challenges that each country must try to solve by 2030. Our approach aims to capture the way in which the various institutional actors are linked to carry out their research and introduce their results in social practice. The main objective is to highlight the transdisciplinary nature of research, based on the way in which academic projects and programs have been structured to meet these 17 challenges in an institution used as a case study.

Materials and Method

A thematic dispersion index was used to identify multidisciplinary institutions in the context of the National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM) (Arencibia-Jorge, Vega-Almeida & Carrillo-Calvet, 2021). The Complexity Science Center (C3), one of the entities with the greatest multidisciplinary scope within the university, was selected as a case study. For the characterization of institutional research, a survey was made of the main research lines developed by the institution, as well as the main external projects led by members of the research staff. During the process, based on the exhaustive analysis of the scientific production generated by each project, the academic programs to which they respond were identified, as well as the SDGs to which their main results contribute.

A network approach was used to highlight the implicit relationships in the projects, using VOSviewer and co-occurrence analysis techniques (Van Eck and Waltman, 2010). The main nodes or vertices represented in networks were academic programs (**pa**, C3 macro programs in which the projects are structured), projects (**p**, C3 projects or research lines), and Sustainable Development Goals (**SDGs**) in which the results of C3 projects have contributed. In the visualization of these links, the nodes or vertices are grouped according to the intensity of their relationships, and the size of **pa** and **SDGs** is determined by the number of projects to which they contribute. SDG 17 (Strategic Alliances) was excluded from the representation, since all C3 projects were the result of strategic alliances inside and outside of the university. In its place, the COVID-19 objective was represented, due to the impact that the pandemic had on all sectors of society since 2020, which required the adaptation of institutional research plans and linking strategies as part of the organizational resilience.

Results and Discussion

During the 2014-2021 period, C3 developed a pipeline of 99 projects, structured into 7 academic programs. *Complexity and Health* (**pa-cs**, 22 projects), *Ecological Complexity and Environment* (**pa-cema**, 21), *Complexity and Systems Biology* (**pa-cbs**, 18) and *Computational Intelligence and Mathematical Modeling* (**pa-icmm**, 16) were the programs that generated the greatest number of projects, with high levels of productivity (high number of articles generated per project). The programs with fewer projects were the most recently developed, such as *Art, Science and Complexity* (**pa-aac**, 9 projects), *Social Complexity and Neurosciences* (**pa-neuro**, 4 projects). *Social Complexity* and *Art, Science and Complexity* were characterized by the systematic generation of exhibitions, seminars and scientific meetings, and bibliometric variables played a less important role.

The multi, inter and transdisciplinary conception of C3 was evidenced from the impact of the 99 projects on all the SDGs (Table 1), as well as the diversity of specialties identified in the curricula of researchers linked to each project (Arencibia-Jorge, Vega-Almeida & Carrillo-Calvet, 2021), and the large number of links between the various programs, projects and SDGs (Figure 1).

Table 1. Sustainable Development Goals where C3 projects contributed.

SDGs	p	SDGs	p	SDGs	p
ods17	99	ods12	12	ods10	6
ods03	42	ods01	11	ods09	5
ods15	38	ods16	11	ods05	4
ods04	24	ods02	8	ods07	4
ods11	24	covid-19	6	ods06	2
ods13	13	ods08	6	ods14	1

The network revealed the diversity of research, the strong interaction between the multiple knowledge domains, and the simultaneous impact of projects and programs on two or more SDGs. Given the social significance of each of these SDGs, this simultaneous impact can be considered as representative element of a transdisciplinary approach of research, from a scientometric perspective. Each of the 14 groups obtained by clustering techniques (different colours in Figure 1) evidenced the same *nexus*. This knowledge integration process implied a wide convergence of disciplines, where *ad hoc* methodological proposals were generated to solved complex problems of strategic relevance for the society. This is in correspondence with the mission of C3, and the objectives defined in its portfolio of research projects.

Figure 1. Network of academic programs, projects, and SDGs (C3, 2014-2020).

Final Considerations

Our case study demonstrated that the use of the SDGs can contribute to the characterization of scientific institutions, as well as the development of bibliometric methods to study the transdisciplinary scope of research at micro level. SDGs introduce the social impact in the analytical approach, which could be combined with interdisciplinarity measures for a more comprehensive study of knowledge integration in institutional domains.

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